

Physico-Chemical Studies of Calcium-Lead Hydroxylapatites. Part III*. X-Ray, Electron-Microscopic and Solubility Equilibria Data

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The lattice constants of calcium-lead hydroxylapatites were found to increase with increase in lead content of the samples resulting in the dilation of the unit cell. The increase in crystal dimensions could also be observed in their electron micrographic patterns of the samples. It was observed that PbHA was less soluble than CaHA at a given pH. In case of solid solutions, (i) the solubility decreased with increase of pH of the dissolving medium and (ii) at a given pH it was found to decrease steadily till about 40.0 mole % of lead hydroxylapatite composition was reached and thereafter an increase in solubility with greater proportions of PbHA in the solid solution. The apatites being salts of a weak acid undergo hydrolysis in aqueous media, the dissolving PO_4^{3-} ions function as proton acceptors accounting for the pH dependence of the solubilities.

As a part of physico-chemical investigation^{1,2} of calcium-lead hydroxylapatite the present paper reports the X-ray, electronmicroscopic and solubilities equilibria studies. While the solubility of calcium hydroxylapatite, $\text{C}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, (CaHA) has been investigated exhaustively³ similar studies on lead hydroxylapatite, $\text{Pb}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, (PbHA) and its solid solutions with CaHA seem not to have been reported. The present work reports the solubility behaviour of (i) lead hydroxylapatite, (ii) pH-dependence of solubilities of solid solutions of calcium and lead hydroxylapatites, and (iii) the influence of the lead content of solid solutions at a convenient fixed pH.

Experimental

Samples of CaHA, PbHA and their solid solutions were prepared by precipitation⁴ at 37° and their molar Ca/P, Pb/P and $\frac{\text{Ca} + \text{Pb}}{\text{P}}$ ratios were determined complexometrically⁵. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were taken using Cu-K_α radiation and Debye-Scherrer camera (UNICAM). The distance between each line on the Debye-Scherrer powder pattern and the point where the transmitted beam would strike the film was measured for all the patterns by a micrometer scale from which the values of d were calculated. The lines were indexed and the lattice parameters a and c were calculated by the well established method of Azaroff⁶. The electronmicrograms were obtained by using Elmiskop-1A with water as dispersion medium while carbon as back

ground. From each micrograph, the length and breadth of a few of the crystals of different dimensions were measured using a comparator and their averages were calculated. The experimental specific surface areas of the samples were calculated taking the crystals to be minute cylinders for approximate purposes. The specific surface areas of the samples were calculated using the formula $\frac{2\pi(r+h)}{rh\delta}$, where

$r = 0.5$ times the average breadth, $h =$ average length and $\delta =$ density of the sample. The density of the samples is measured by specific gravity bottle method using toluene as a solvent. The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro analytical determination of phosphate in the saturated solutions of the samples. 0.2 g of each of the samples sieved to 200 mesh (BSS) was equilibrated with 100 ml. of the buffer in polythene containers by mechanical shaking at (37±0.5°) to stimulate biological conditions. In each case the phases were separated by filtration through an IG₄ crucible and the calcium and phosphorus, in the case of the calcium hydroxylapatite systems, lead and phosphorus in case of lead hydroxylapatite and only phosphorus in the case of the solid solutions were determined complexometrically. The period for saturation in each case was ascertained by the presence of same quantity of phosphorus in the filtrate after the specified time interval. Potassium hydrogen phthalate-sodium hydroxide buffer combinations were used to maintain the dissolution medium at pH 5.0 to 6.5 while veronal-hydrochloric acid buffer combinations were used for pH 7.0 to 8.0. The mechanism of dissolution of PbHA was investigated at a pH 5.5.

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Fig. 1. Electronmicrographs of the samples. (Refer Table 1, samples 1, 3 and 6 respectively). Magnification in each case is 80,000 $\times$.

Results and Discussion

The results of analyses and the values of lattice constant of CaHA, PbHA and their solid solutions are included in Table 1. It is seen that the lattice constants increased with increase in lead content of

medium from 5.0 to 8.0 and (ii) that at a fixed pH it decreased upto 40.0 mole percent of PbHA in the solid solution but thereafter a steady increase occurred (Fig. 2). The dissolution of CaHA involves hydrolysis of hydroxylapatite lattice leading to the

TABLE 1. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM-LEAD HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR LATTICE PARAMETERS AND SPECIFIC SURFACE AREA

Sample No.	Wt%			Molecular formulae	Lattice parameters ($\text{\AA}$)		Specific surface area (m^2/g)
	Ca	Pb	P		a	c	
1	39.39	—	18.16	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	9.37	6.91	14.7
2	24.57	29.85	14.07	$\text{Ca}_{8.1}\text{Pb}_{1.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	9.42	6.93	14.3
3	14.45	49.39	11.14	$\text{Ca}_6\text{Pb}_4(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	9.51	7.01	9.7
4	8.90	52.58	9.65	$\text{Ca}_{4.3}\text{Pb}_{5.7}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	9.63	7.02	7.8
5	3.78	70.44	8.07	$\text{Ca}_{2.1}\text{Pb}_{7.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	9.71	7.14	6.2
6	—	77.43	6.95	$\text{Pb}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	9.86	7.22	6.0

the samples resulting in the dilation of the unit cell and the consequent decrease in the specific surface area and increase in the crystal dimensions could also be observed in their electron micrographic patterns of the samples (Fig. 1). The crystals became broader with higher proportions of lead content in the samples. It is observed that the solubility of all the samples (i) decreased with increase of pH of the dissolving

formation⁷ of tricalcium phosphate and lime according to the following equations.

Tricalcium phosphate would have the lower solubility compared with lime and in general the

Fig. 2. Solubility equilibria data of calcium and lead hydroxylapatites.

precipitation of basic phosphates is governed by the solubility products of the hydroxides⁷, allowing for the common ion effects where required. Exactly analogous equations can be written for the lead species. The only difference is that the equilibrium (b) lies more to the left; this accounts for the lower solubility of PbHA at a given pH. Thus basically CaHA and PbHA undergo the same mode of dissolution. The observed pH-dependence of the solubilities of the samples and the initial decrease of solubility upto 40 mole per cent of PbHA in solid solution can be explained by the common ion effect. Thereafter the solubility is expected to increase where there is sufficient increase in PbHA to appreciably destabilise the crystal lattice—a well known phenomena in case of allotropes, less stable allotropes are more soluble. Arogonite (orthorhombic) is less stable and hence greater solubility than calcite having a more symmetrical rhombohedral crystal lattice. Thus the increase in the trend of the solubility of solid solutions with higher proportions of PbHA could be explained.

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